

Supplementary Information

Pontine waves accompanied by short hippocampal sharp wave-ripples during non-rapid eye movement sleep

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Supplementary Figure 1. Average power spectral density in each state.

High theta (~7 Hz) power was apparent during REM sleep (*arrow*). Note that due to the variability of low-cut filter settings across experiments, low frequency (<1 Hz) power did not reflect real signals. AW, wakefulness; NREM, NREM sleep; REM, REM sleep. Errors indicate SEM.

Supplementary Figure 2. P-wave frequency across the sleep-wake cycle.

Circle, silicon probe recording. *Cross mark*, bipolar electrode recording. *******, $p < 0.0001$ (Kruskal-Wallis test with post-hoc Bonferroni method).

Supplementary Figure 3. P-wave-associated calcium transients in mesopontine cholinergic neurons.

The modulation index was defined as $(F_{post} - F_{pre}) / (F_{post} + F_{pre})$, where F_{pre} and F_{post} are normalized fluorescent signals 1 s before and after P-wave timing, respectively. Wilcoxon signed-rank test was performed to examine if the median is zero.

Supplementary Figure 4. P-wave-associated brainstem neural ensemble dynamics on a long timescale.

Brainstem neural activity during NREM sleep (**A**) and REM sleep (**B**). *top*, heat map of perievent time histograms across recorded neurons. Neurons were sorted by the first principal component of the heat map during REM sleep. Individual neuronal activity was Z-scored. *bottom*, the average of Z-scored activity. (**C**) Pearson's correlation coefficient at different window sizes. As the window size increases, the correlation coefficient decreases ($p < 0.0001$, Kruskal-Wallis test).

Supplementary Figure 5. Theta-P-wave coupling during REM sleep.

Phase histograms of P-wave timing relative to hippocampal theta rhythms across recordings ($n = 7$). *P*-values, Rayleigh's test. *Red line*, a theta cycle (4 – 10 Hz).

Supplementary Figure 6. The effect of window size on ripple power change after P-waves.

Related to **Figure 4E**, different window sizes were examined. After calculating the asymmetry index, *t*-test was performed to examine if the mean is zero. P-values were shown as a function of window size.

Supplementary Figure 7. The relationship between coupling window size and statistical assessment.

(A) Cohen's U3 as a function of coupling window size. Errors indicate 95% confidence intervals. (B) P-values (rank-sum test) as a function of coupling window size.

Supplementary Figure 8. CA1 firing at P-wave timing depending on SWR coupling.

CA1 firing at P-wave timing was separated depending on coupling to SWRs within a 30 ms (**A**) or longer time window (**B**). *top*, heat map of normalized peri-event time histograms across neurons. Individual neural activity was normalized by peak firing rate to 1. Neurons were sorted by the first principal component in each heat map. *bottom*, the modulation index was defined as $(FR_{post} - FR_{pre}) / (FR_{post} + FR_{pre})$, where FR_{pre} and FR_{post} are normalized firing rate 250 ms before and after P-wave timing, respectively. *t*-test was performed to examine if the mean is zero.

Supplementary Figure 9. Spectral Independence Criterion analysis between hippocampal and pontine LFPs.

(A) A schematic drawing outlines the motivation for this analysis. (B) An algorithm to compute the spectral density ratio based on the Spectral Independence Criterion (SIC). The interpretation of the outcome is also shown at the bottom. (C) The difference between $p_{X \rightarrow Y}$ and $p_{Y \rightarrow X}$. The smaller value implies a stronger causal direction from pontine to hippocampal LFPs. *, $p < 0.05$ (signed rank test).